
IMPACT OF GREEN MARKETING ON CONSUMER PURCHASE BEHAVIOUR TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE PRODUCTS

Ms. Pooja Gupta

Assistant Professor, Niranjana Majithia College of commerce, Mumbai

ABSTRACT

Green marketing has become an important strategy for promoting environmentally friendly products and encouraging sustainable consumption. This study examines the impact of green marketing on consumer purchase behaviour towards sustainable products. Primary data was collected from 35 respondents in Mumbai using a structured questionnaire through convenience sampling. The findings show that most consumers are aware of green marketing and have a positive attitude toward eco-friendly products. Green advertisements, eco-labels, and environmental information influence consumer purchase decisions. However, factors such as price, product quality, and brand reputation also affect buying behaviour. The study concludes that effective green marketing and affordable pricing can increase consumer adoption of sustainable products.

Keywords: *Green Marketing, Consumer Purchase Behaviour, Sustainable Products, Eco-friendly Products, Consumer Awareness, Sustainable Consumption*

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, environmental concerns such as climate change, pollution, and depletion of natural resources have become more serious worldwide. Because of these problems, companies, governments, and people to adopt more sustainable practices. Sustainability has become an important part of modern business strategies and planning. Organizations are now working to focus on eco-friendly practices to reduce harm and meet customer demands.

Green marketing is now an important way for businesses to sell eco-friendly products and promote sustainable practices. Green marketing focuses on creating and selling products or services that are eco-friendly and sustainable. Companies are promoting products with eco-labels, eco-friendly packaging, energy-saving production, and careful advertising to attract environmentally aware customers.

Customers are now paying attention to the environmental problem and moving toward sustainable products. Green marketing helps consumers understand why products are good by highlighting the environmental advantages of products also it influences how they think and what they buy. By sharing their eco-friendly practices companies can strengthen trust and loyalty among customers.

Although sustainability is growing, we need to know how green marketing shapes consumer choices. Even though many consumers know environmental problem consumers' choices are affected by price, quality, and brand.

This study looks at how green marketing changes consumers' choices for eco-friendly goods. The main goal of this research is to understand what customers knowledge, feelings, attitudes, and what drives them to buy eco-friendly items. Companies can use the results of this research in promoting eco-friendly products and influencing sustainable buying decisions.

Significance of the Study

The research highlights the role of ESG practices and explains how they support sustainability and lasting performance. The study shows organizations, investors, and policymakers why making ethical and responsible decisions is important. The study contributes ESG concepts easier to understand and how they work in real life. Overall, following ESG principles supports is important for growth, a positive image and compete better.

Scope of the Study

The research focuses on urban consumers, who see more eco-friendly campaigns to understand their choices of sustainable products. The study checks consumers' awareness, opinions and how green marketing affects their decisions. Factors such as product price, quality, brand reputation, and environmental concern are checked to understand their impact on buying sustainable products. The study used structured questionnaires to collect information from respondents, showing real consumer views and buying behaviour. The research is limited to a certain sample and region but it provides valuable knowledge about the role of green marketing in promoting green purchases.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A study by Jeevarathnam Govender and Tushya L. Govender (2016) examined the influence of green marketing on consumer purchase behaviour. The study used a survey of 100 consumers and adopted a quantitative research design to analyze consumer perceptions toward environmentally friendly products. The findings revealed that consumers generally have high awareness of environmental issues and green marketing practices. The study also found that green marketing activities such as promotion, packaging, and product information positively influence consumers' purchasing decisions. However, the results indicated that price sensitivity remains a major barrier, as many consumers perceive green products as expensive despite recognizing their environmental and health benefits.

A study by **Mokha (2017)** examined consumer perception toward eco-friendly products in the context of green marketing. The study highlighted that increasing environmental problems such as pollution and climate change have encouraged consumers to become more environmentally conscious. The research collected primary data through a structured questionnaire from **152 respondents** and used statistical tools for analysis. The findings revealed that a large number of consumers are aware of eco-friendly products and show positive attitudes toward them. However, the study also found that although consumers support environmentally friendly products, many are hesitant to pay higher prices. The study concluded that effective green marketing strategies and increased awareness can encourage sustainable consumer behaviour.

In the study Green Marketing, Kusuma and Asifulla (2024) explain that green marketing is a key strategy for sustainable development in modern business. The study highlights rising environmental awareness among consumers and the importance of eco-friendly products, packaging, and promotional practices. It also addresses challenges such as greenwashing, which can reduce consumer trust if companies make false environmental claims. Furthermore, the paper emphasizes the role of government regulations and ethical marketing practices in promoting sustainability. The findings suggest that effective green marketing not only enhances brand image and consumer trust but also contributes to long-term environmental protection and competitive advantage for businesses.

Vrutika Desai and Krupa Bhatt (2024) in their study "Green Marketing: A Study of Consumers' Purchasing Behavior of Selected Eco-Friendly Products" examined consumer awareness and purchasing behaviour toward eco-friendly products. The study found that increasing environmental awareness has encouraged consumers to adopt green purchasing habits. It also identified that factors such as product quality, price, availability, and environmental knowledge significantly influence consumer buying decisions. However, the study also highlights those higher prices and limited availability of eco-friendly products act as barriers to the widespread adoption of green products.

Monika Bhatia and Amit Jain (2014) in their study "Green Marketing: A Study of Consumer Perception and Preferences in India" analysed consumer awareness and preferences toward green products in India. The study revealed that consumers have high awareness and positive environmental values. It also found that awareness, green values, and perception of environmentally responsible companies influence consumer purchase decisions. However, price and product availability remain major challenges, and the study concludes that effective marketing communication is necessary to promote green products and encourage e sustainable consumption.

OBJECTIVES

1. To examine the level of consumer awareness regarding green marketing and sustainable products.
2. To analyse the impact of green marketing strategies on consumer purchase behaviour.
3. To study consumers' attitudes towards eco-friendly and sustainable products.
4. To identify the key factors influencing consumers to purchase sustainable products.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY**Research Design**

The study adopts a descriptive research design to analyze the impact of green marketing on consumer purchase behaviour towards sustainable products.

Data Collection

Primary data was collected using a structured questionnaire consisting of close-ended questions through Google Forms. Secondary data was gathered from research journals, books, articles, and websites related to green marketing and consumer behaviour.

Sampling Design

A convenience sampling method was used to select respondents based on their accessibility and willingness to participate. The sample size comprised 35 respondents from the Western Suburbs of Mumbai.

Data Analysis

The collected data was compiled and analyzed using simple statistical tools, mainly percentage analysis, to understand consumer awareness, attitudes, and factors influencing their purchase behaviour towards sustainable products.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Question	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Strongly Disagree	Disagree
I am aware of the concept of green marketing.	34.30%	34.30%	28.60%	2.8%	0%
I am aware of eco-friendly or sustainable products available in the market	17.10%	57.10%	20%	5.8%	0%
I notice eco-labels or environmental claims on product packaging	17.10%	48.60%	22.90%	2.8%	8.60%
Companies promote environmentally friendly products through advertisements and marketing campaigns.	25.70%	37.10%	28.60%	5.8%	2.8%
Green advertisements influence my purchase decisions.	14.30%	48.60%	22.90%	5.6%	8.60%
I prefer buying products from companies that follow environmentally sustainable practices.	22.90%	42.90%	28.60%	2.8%	2.8%
Environmental information provided in marketing campaigns affects my buying behaviour.	22.90%	42.90%	28.60%	0%	5.6%
I am more likely to purchase a product if it is marketed as eco-friendly	22.90%	42.90%	25.70%	5.7%	2.8%
Eco-friendly products help in protecting the environment.	28.60%	45.70%	20%	5.7%	0%
I feel responsible for supporting sustainable products through my purchases	22.90%	51.40%	20%	2.8%	2.9%
I prefer brands that are environmentally responsible.	20%	40%	34.30%	5.7%	0%
I have a positive attitude toward companies practicing green marketing	25.70%	51.40%	17.10%	5.8%	0%
The quality of eco-friendly products influences my purchase decision.	22.90%	42.90%	31.40%	0%	2.8%
The price of eco-friendly products affects my willingness to buy them	25.70%	34.30%	34.30%	0%	5.7%
Brand reputation influences my purchase of sustainable products	20%	40%	34.30%	2.8%	2.9%
My environmental concern motivates me to buy eco-friendly products	22.90%	34.30%	42.90%	0%	0%

Objective 1: To examine the level of consumer awareness regarding green marketing and sustainable products

The survey shows that most consumers are aware of green marketing and sustainable products. About 68.6% of respondents are aware of green marketing, while 74.2% are aware of eco-friendly products available in the market. Many respondents also notice eco-labels and environmental claims on product packaging. This indicates a good level of awareness among consumers, although some respondents remain neutral.

Objective 2: To analyse the impact of green marketing strategies on consumer purchase behaviour

The findings show that green marketing strategies influence consumer buying behaviour. Many respondents agree that companies promote eco-friendly products through advertisements and marketing campaigns. Around 62.9% of respondents agree that green advertisements influence their purchase decisions. Environmental information in marketing campaigns also affects consumers' buying behaviour, showing the importance of green promotion.

Objective 3: To study consumers' attitudes towards eco-friendly and sustainable products

The results indicate that consumers have a positive attitude toward eco-friendly products. Most respondents believe that eco-friendly products help protect the environment and feel responsible for supporting sustainable products. Many consumers also prefer brands that follow environmentally responsible practices and have a positive view of companies practicing green marketing.

Objective 4: To identify the key factors influencing consumers to purchase sustainable products

The survey shows that product quality, price, brand reputation, and environmental concern are important factors influencing purchase decisions. Consumers are more likely to buy eco-friendly products if they are of good quality and from reputable brands. However, the price of sustainable products also affects consumers' willingness to purchase them.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. The study uses a small sample and may not represent all consumers.
2. Research is limited to certain urban areas; results may differ elsewhere.
3. Time constraints limited data collection.
4. Results depend on respondents' honesty and understanding.
5. Only a few factors like awareness, attitude, price, quality, and brand are considered.

FINDINGS

1. The survey included **35 respondents**, mostly **male (71%)** and **female (29%)**. Most participants were **below 20 years (54.3%)**, followed by **21–30 years (42.9%)**.
2. Education levels were mainly **Higher Secondary and Graduate (37.1% each)**. A large majority were **students (80%)**, and **71.4% earned below ₹20,000 per month**, indicating a young, low-income sample.
3. The study reveals that a majority of the respondents are aware of the concept of green marketing. About **68.6% of respondents** stated that they are aware of green marketing, while **74.2% are aware of eco-friendly or sustainable products available in the market**.
4. The results show that many consumers pay attention to environmental information on products. Around **65.7% of respondents notice eco-labels or environmental claims on product packaging**, which indicates increasing environmental awareness among consumers.
5. The study found that **green marketing strategies significantly influence consumer purchase behaviour**. About **62.8% of respondents believe that companies promote eco-friendly products through advertisements**, and **62.9% stated that green advertisements influence their purchase decisions**.
6. Environmental information provided in marketing campaigns also plays an important role. Around **65.8% of respondents stated that such information affects their buying behaviour and makes them more likely to purchase eco-friendly products**.
7. The findings indicate that consumers have a **positive attitude towards eco-friendly products**. About **74.3% of respondents believe that eco-friendly products help protect the environment**, and the same percentage feel responsible for supporting sustainable products through their purchases.
8. The study also found that **77.1% of respondents have a positive attitude toward companies practicing green marketing**, and **60% prefer brands that are environmentally responsible**.
9. Several factors influence the purchase of sustainable products. **Product quality influences 65.8% of respondents**, while **60% stated that the price of eco-friendly products affects their willingness to buy**.
10. **Brand reputation influences 60% of respondents**, and **57.2% stated that their environmental concern motivates them to purchase eco-friendly products**.

RECOMMENDATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

1. Companies should try to reduce the cost of eco-friendly products so that they become more affordable and accessible to a larger number of consumers.
2. Sustainable products should match or exceed the quality of regular products in order to build consumer trust and satisfaction.
3. More awareness and educational campaigns should be conducted to increase environmental concern and knowledge among consumers.
4. Clear and visible eco-labels should be used on product packaging so that consumers can easily identify environmentally friendly products.
5. Companies should build a strong and trustworthy green brand image to positively influence consumer buying behaviour.
6. Social media and other digital marketing platforms should be used to effectively promote eco-friendly products, especially among young consumers.
7. Government policies, subsidies, and incentives should support both producers and consumers in adopting sustainable practices.
8. Companies should provide transparent and genuine information about their environmental practices and avoid misleading claims or greenwashing.

CONCLUSION

1. The study concludes that green marketing plays an important role in influencing consumer purchase behaviour towards sustainable products. Consumers today are highly aware of environmental issues and show a positive attitude toward eco-friendly products and brands.
2. Green marketing strategies such as eco-labeling, green advertisements, and environmental information have a strong impact on consumer decisions. Most consumers prefer to buy from companies that follow sustainable practices and trust that eco-friendly products help protect the environment.
3. However, despite high awareness and positive attitudes, factors such as price, product quality, and brand reputation continue to influence purchase decisions. Price remains a major barrier, as many consumers are not willing to pay a premium for eco-friendly products.
4. Overall, the study shows that while green marketing is effective in shaping consumer behaviour, companies must balance sustainability with affordability and quality to increase adoption of sustainable products.

REFERENCES

1. Bhatia, M., & Jain, A. (2014). Green marketing: A study of consumer perception and preferences in India. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341095497>
2. Desai, V., & Bhatt, K. (2024). Green marketing: A study of consumers' purchasing behavior of selected eco-friendly products. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/383405409>
3. Kusuma, & Asifulla. (2024). Green marketing. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/377895951>
4. Mokha, A. K. (2017). *Green marketing: A study of consumer perception on using eco-friendly products*. *Asian Journal of Research in Business Economics and Management*, 7(8), 298–309. <https://doi.org/10.5958/2249-7307.2017.00146.3>
5. Govender, J. P., & Govender, T. L. (2016). *The influence of green marketing on consumer purchase behavior*. *Environmental Economics*, 7(2), 77–85. [https://doi.org/10.21511/ee.07\(2\).2016.8](https://doi.org/10.21511/ee.07(2).2016.8)
6. Environmental Protection Agency – Sustainability <https://www.epa.gov/sustainability>
7. Investopedia – Green Marketing Definition <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/g/green-marketing.asp>
8. Statista – Sustainability and Consumer Behavior Statistics <https://www.statista.com/topics/4401/sustainability/>
9. Environmental Marketing – Polonsky, M. J., & Rosenberger, P. (2001). *Environmental Marketing: Strategies, Practice, Theory and Research*. Routledge.